

THE APPROACHES FOR DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

*F. Shukurova*¹

Abstract:

This article is about the ways and approaches for the development of students' communicative competence according to several scientific and pedagogical researches on the concept of communicative competence.

Key words: communicative competence, teaching foreign language, approach, language skills, communicative approach.

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The result of cultural and economic development of relations among countries and societies is increasing the demand for the people or specialists who speak in foreign languages. These days the most important areas of education are using mostly competency-based approach. The utterance is about developing skills related to the practical application of a person's communicative skills, his cultural, social, and information competencies. In scientific and pedagogical references, this issue is widely discussed, but a cognitive approach prevails in higher education, and students usually have to remember huge amount of information instead of developing the basic competencies needed for successful work.

Recently, the concepts of "communicative" and "communicative approach" have been widely used in the field of foreign language learning. According to foreign methodological references, this concept is referred to communicative teaching or communicative approach. In other words, these terms mean so called approach which the communication is considered teaching a foreign language, in which communication is considered both a tool and an objective of study during the process of interaction with a partner.

This approach was emerged in 1970s and 1980s owing to great deal of studies and researches in Europe and the USA.

The main component of communicative competence is based on language skills, as well as linguistic and cultural studies. The principle of communication leads to the need for properly organized teaching and using different forms of methodology for communicating.

Communicative competence represents various aspects of scientific interests of scientists such as I.R. Altunina, V.I. Kashnitskiy, A.V. Molozhavenko, Yu.V. Mryakina, E.V. Prozorova and many other experts.

However, the results of an analysis of communicative competence as an interdisciplinary phenomenon are hardly any found among the studies of scholars. Therefore, we believe that a gradual review of communicative competence is very helpful for creating its theoretical model, firstly, as an event and then as a pedagogical category.

Named experts of linguistics and education, the authors of many professional articles and textbooks, J. Richards and T. Rogers express their views on the sphere of communicative

¹ *Shukurova Farida, Doctorate student of SamSIFL*

teaching of a foreign language. They believe that communication is mostly approach than a language teaching method. They describe the communicative approach of language learning using certain principles and objectives, as the methods of students' language learning process, the types of tasks and exercises used in teaching, and the role of a teacher and a student in learning languages [4,94]. According to this approach, the main principles of teaching are:

- Communicative principle: learning promotes real communication through practice;
- Principle of developmental tasks: learning is carried out through exercises that use the language to accomplish interesting and regarded tasks;
- Principle of importance and content: learning is carried out using meaningful phrases in the target language. Educational tasks are selected depending on how actively the student interacts in real communication (unlike the mechanical use of language models).

As part of "communicative competence" the following elements are distinguished:

- linguistic (knowledge about the language system and their usage for understanding other people's speech and expressing one's own mind);
- socio-cultural (knowledge about the ethnic and cultural characteristics of the target language, the oral speech and gestures of native speakers, and the ability of performing body language according to that knowledge);
- speech (forming the ideas with the help of foreign language and the ability of using those ideas during oral communication); discourse (being informed about the rules of written and oral speech formation and understanding the messages of communicators while they are speaking);
- strategic (the ability of using the most effective strategies to solve communication problems)
- compensation (difficulties in oral communication ability to overcome); pragmatic (the ability of choosing the most effective and correct way to express the idea depending on the terms of communication task).

To understand the approaches to developing individual components of the communicative competence, we have to turn back a history of teaching foreign languages. The researches led by A.V. Mirolyubov, I.V. Rakhmanov, K.A. Ganshina, I.A. Gruzinskaya, Z.M. Tsvetkova, S.K. Folomkina, N.I. Gez, Yu.A. Jluktenko, R.A. Kuznets in the history of foreign language teaching methodology allow us to study this sphere profoundly.

According to this theory, the concept of communication is from two points of view: theoretical, i.e. category (concept) and practical (empirical), i.e. technology. E.I. Passov, who interpreted the dialogue as teaching technology or strategy, identifies the following characteristics:

Russian scientist, founder of Lipetsk Methodological School, Doctor of Pedagogy E.I. Passov created his own communicative foreign language education theory. According to this theory, the concept of communication is considered from two points of view: theoretical, i.e. category (concept) and practical (empirical), i.e. technology. E.I. Passov, who interpreted the dialogue as teaching technology or strategy, identifies the following characteristics:

- Motivate students each attempt and activity;
- The complicity of students' attempts and activities;
- The existence of objective in all the work of the students;

The process of speech and cognition that is to say, the presence of logic in the process of solving problems with the help of speech, i.e. a constant relationship between cognitive and communicative thinking for solving communication problems.

- A personal interest that involves expressing a personal attitude to problems and topics to be discussed.

- The relationship between communication and various forms of activities such as, education, society, labor, sports, art, and household.

- The interaction of communicators, i.e. the coordination of movements, assistance, support for each other, reliable cooperation. Contact in three stages: emotional, semantic and personal [3,124].

Functionality or the process of absorbing speech materials, always occurs with the participation of speech functions that are superior to the shape of speech units.

Content and subjective as an objective characteristic of learning materials informativeness as characteristics;

Expressions in the use of problematic, oral and non-verbal communication tools as a way to organize and present educational materials.

Observing all listed parameters and using them acceptably gives you the opportunity of calling the learning process as communicative. This sample model forms the basis of this concept.

To sum up, the communicative approach of teaching foreign languages allows teachers organize their own classes and communicate in any language, using interesting chat topics for students imagining their real lives.

Instead, it should be noted that the communicative method of teaching foreign languages is objectively the most effective, and the main functions of this style are: – teaching foreign language as a means of communication;

– training students to consider a foreign language not as an object of constant learning but as a convenient and necessary means of practical communication.

References:

- [1]. Chomskiy N. *“Language and mind”* Cambridge University Press. – 2006 - 205p.
- [2]. Gorbatova T.N. *“The active communication approach for teaching foreign languages in non-philological universities”/ T.N. Gorbatova, A.V. Kudryashova, S.V. Rybushkin. – Molodoe uchyony. – 2015. – No10 (90) – P. 1139-1141.*
- [3]. Passov E.I. *“Communicative approach of teaching foreign language”*. – M.: Academia, 2005y. 397p.
- [4]. Savignon, Sandra J. *“Teaching communicative language”* London: Routledge, 2000. 125p